

Image and Video Completion by Using Bayesian Tensor Decomposition

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Abstract

Reconstruction of image and video from sparse observations attract a great deal of interest in the field of image/video compression, feature extraction and denoising. Since the color image and video data can be naturally expressed as a tensor structure, many methods based on tensor algebra have been studied together with promising predictive performance. However, one challenging problem in those methods is tuning parameters empirically which usually requires computational demanding cross validation or intuitive selection. In this paper, we introduce Bayesian Tucker decomposition to reconstruct image and video data from incomplete observation. By specifying the sparsity priors over factor matrices and core tensor, the tensor rank can be automatically inferred via variational bayesian, which greatly reduce the computational cost for model selection. We conduct several experiments on image and video data, which shows that our method outperforms the other tensor methods in terms of completion performance. **Keywords:** *Image completion, Tensor completion, Bayesian Tucker decomposition.*

1. Introduction

Image or video completion, which is to reconstruct a full image/video from only sparsely observed information, plays an important role in image processing field. Image data can be naturally expressed as a 3rd-order tensor of size $height \times width \times color\ channel$, while the video data can be represented as 4th-order tensor of size $height \times width \times color \times time$. Tensor is an extension of vectors and matrices to the high order case, which enables us to represent the structured data. The traditional way to handle such data is firstly transforming the data into the vector or

matrix form, then many existing algorithms based on matrix analysis can be employed for image and video processing. However, the adjacent structure information of original data will be lost [1] due to the matricization operations. To overcome this limitation, tensor analysis methods are the emerging technology, which attracts a great deal of attentions in recent years. By using multilinear algebra, tensor decomposition can efficiently exploit the intrinsic high order structure information within the data and provide better interpretability. The most popular models of tensor decomposition are Tucker decomposition [2] and CANDECOMP/PARAFAC (CP) decomposition [3–5]. Moreover, tensor method has been applied in various research field such as: image completion [6–14], signal processing [15–21], brain machine interface (BMI) [22–24], image classification [25, 26], face recognition [27], machine learning [28], etc. Basically, there are two type of methods for tensor completion. One type is based on minimization of the convex relaxation function of tensor rank by using nuclear norm of tensor. The nuclear norm can be defined in several different ways related to the different tensor decomposition models. By applying the appropriate optimization algorithm, we can find the optimal low-rank tensor as the approximation of full tensor. Another type is based on tensor decomposition of incomplete tensor. The specific algorithm must be developed to find latent factors under the specific tensor decomposition model by using partially observed entries. It is necessary to predefine the tensor rank, which is considered as a model selection problem. Although cross-validation can be used to determine an optimal tensor rank, it is quite computational demanding. Especially, when the Tucker decomposition is considered, the number of possibilities of tensor rank increases exponentially to the order of tensor.

To overcome these limitations, we introduce a Bayesian tensor decomposition method to perform image and video com-

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Fig. 1: First, second, thrid-order tensor

pletion. Our methods can automatically adapt model complexity and infer an optimal multilinear rank by the principle of maximum lower bound of model evidence. Experimental results and comparisons on image and video data demonstrate remarkable performance of our models for recovering the groundtruth of multilinear rank and missing pixels.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly overviews the Tucker decomposition and CANDECOMP/PARAFAC (CP) decomposition. Section III describes the Bayesian Tucker decomposition method and the corresponding inference algorithm. Section IV shows the experimental results on real-world image and video data. Finally, we summarize our paper in Section V.

2. Tensor decompositions

Tensor is a multidimensional array which is a generalization of vectors and matrices to higher dimensions. First-order tensor is a vector, second-order tensor is a matrix, and third or higher order tensor is higher-order tensor. First, second, third-order tensor are shown in Fig. 1. Tensor decompositions originated from Hitchcock [29] [30]. Under the work of Tucker [31] [32] [2], Carroll and Chang [3], Harshman [4], Appellof and Davidson [33], the tensor theory and tensor decompositions (factorizations) algorithms have been successfully applied to various fields, examples include signal processing, computer vision and etc.

2.1 Notation

The order of a tensor is the number of dimensions [34]. Tensor of order one (vector) is denoted by boldface lowercase letters, e.g., \mathbf{a} , the i -th element of a one-order tensor is denoted by a_i . Tensor of order two (matrix) is denoted by boldface capital letters, e.g., \mathbf{A} , the (i, j) element of a two-order tensor is denoted by a_{ij} . Tensor of order three

or higher (higher-order tensor) is denoted by boldface Euler script letters, e.g., \mathcal{X} , the (i, j, k) element of a three-order tensor is denoted by x_{ijk} . Indices typically range from 1 to their capital version, e.g., $i = 1, \dots, I$.

2.2 CP decomposition

CANDECOMP/PARAFAC (CP) decomposition method is proposed by Carroll and Chang [3] and PARAFAC (parallel factors) proposed by Harshman [4]. Usually, we refer to the CANDECOMP/PARAFAC decomposition as CP [5]. CP decomposition is to represent a tensor as the sum of R rank-one tensors. For example, given a third-order tensor $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{I \times J \times K}$, we wish to represent it by (1) (2).

$$\mathcal{X} = \sum_{r=1}^R \mathbf{a}_r \circ \mathbf{b}_r \circ \mathbf{c}_r = [\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}]. \quad (1)$$

$$x_{ijk} = \sum_{r=1}^R a_{ir} b_{jr} c_{kr}, \quad (2)$$

$$\forall i = 1, \dots, I, \forall j = 1, \dots, J, \forall k = 1, \dots, K.$$

where $\mathbf{a}_r \in \mathbb{R}^I$, $\mathbf{b}_r \in \mathbb{R}^J$ and $\mathbf{c}_r \in \mathbb{R}^K$, $\forall r = 1, \dots, R$. The rank of a tensor \mathcal{X} , denoted by $R = \text{rank}(\mathcal{X})$, is define as the smallest number of rank-one tensors that can exactly represent \mathcal{X} . The scheme of CP decompositions is illustrated in Fig. 2.

2.3 Tucker decomposition

The Tucker decomposition is proposed firstly in 1963 [35], and refined in subsequent articles by Levin [33] and Tucker [2, 32]. Tucker decomposition can be considered as a form of higher-order PCA (Principal Components Analysis), which

Fig. 2: CP decomposition of a third-order tensor

decomposes a tensor into a core tensor multiplied (or transformed) by several matrices along each mode. For instance, given a third-order tensor $\mathcal{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{I \times J \times K}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{X} &= \mathcal{G} \times_1 \mathbf{A} \times_2 \mathbf{B} \times_3 \mathbf{C} \\ &= \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{r=1}^R g_{pqr} \circ \mathbf{a}_p \circ \mathbf{b}_q \circ \mathbf{c}_r \\ &= [\mathcal{G}; \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}]. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) can be also written by the element-wise form, which is

$$x_{ijk} \approx \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{r=1}^R g_{pqr} a_{ip} b_{jq} c_{kr}, \quad (4)$$

$$\forall i = 1, \dots, I, \forall j = 1, \dots, J, \forall k = 1, \dots, K.$$

Here, $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{I \times P}$, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{J \times Q}$ and $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times R}$ are the factor matrices, which are usually orthogonal, and can be thought of as the principal components in each mode. Tensor $\mathcal{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{P \times Q \times R}$ is called the *core tensor* and its entries show the level of interaction between the different components. The last equality in (3) uses the shorthand $[\mathcal{G}; \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}]$ which was introduced in [34]. The scheme of Tucker decompositions is illustrated in Fig. 3.

3. Bayesian Tucker decompositions

In this section, we introduce Bayesian Tucker decomposition for tensor completion. Let \mathcal{Y} be an incomplete tensor with missing entries, and \mathcal{O} is a binary tensor which indicates the observation positions. Ω denotes a set of N -tuple indices of observed entries. The value of \mathcal{O} is defined by

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{O}_{i_1 \dots i_N} = 1 & \text{if } (i_1, \dots, i_N) \in \Omega, \\ \mathcal{O}_{i_1 \dots i_N} = 0 & \text{if } (i_1, \dots, i_N) \notin \Omega. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

\mathcal{Y}_Ω is a tensor which only include observed entries. The generative model is assumed as

$$\mathcal{Y}_\Omega = \mathcal{X}_\Omega + \varepsilon, \quad (6)$$

where the latent tensor \mathcal{X} is represented exactly by a Tucker model with a low multilinear rank and ε denotes i.i.d. Gaussian noise.

Given an incomplete image tensor, Bayesian Tucker model only considers the observed data, thus the likelihood function can be represented by

$$p(\mathcal{Y}_\Omega) = \prod_{(i_1, i_2, i_3) \in \Omega} \mathcal{N}(\mathcal{Y}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \mid \mathcal{X}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}, \tau^{-1}). \quad (7)$$

Since the latent tensor \mathcal{X} can be decomposed exactly by a Tucker model, we can thus represent the observation model as that $\forall (i_1, i_2, i_3)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Y}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \mid \{\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)}\}, \mathcal{G}, \tau &\sim \\ \mathcal{N}\left(\left(\bigotimes_n \mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)T}\right) \text{vec}(\mathcal{G}), \tau^{-1}\right)^{\mathcal{O}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $n = 1, 2, 3$. $\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)}$ is the i_n -th row of the factor matrix $\mathbf{U}^{(n)}$, \mathcal{O} is the indicator of missing points. τ is the precision of Gaussian noise.

To employ sparsity priors, we can specify the hierarchical prior distributions by

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &\sim Ga(a_0^\tau, b_0^\tau), \\ \text{vec}(\mathcal{G}) \mid \{\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(n)}\}, \beta &\sim \mathcal{N}\left\{\mathbf{0}, \left(\beta \bigotimes_n \boldsymbol{\Lambda}^{(n)}\right)^{-1}\right\}, \\ \beta &\sim Ga(a_0^\beta, b_0^\beta), \\ \mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)} \mid \boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(n)} &\sim \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Lambda}^{(n)-1}\right), \quad \forall n, \forall i_n. \\ \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{r_n}^{(n)} &\sim Ga(a_0^\lambda, b_0^\lambda), \quad \forall n, \forall r_n, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 3: Tucker decomposition of a third-order tensor

where β is a scale parameter related to the magnitude of \mathcal{G} , on which a hyperprior can be placed. The hyperprior for $\lambda^{(n)}$ play a key role for different sparsity inducing priors. We propose the hierarchical prior corresponding to the Student-t distribution for group sparsity. Note that $\Lambda^{(n)} = \text{diag}(\lambda^{(n)})$.

For Tucker decomposition of an incomplete tensor, the problem is ill-conditioned and has infinite solutions. The low-rank assumption play an key role for successful tensor completion, which implies that the determination of multilinear rank significantly affects the predictive performance. However, standard model selection strategies, such as cross-validation, cannot be applied for finding the optimal multilinear rank because it varies dramatically with missing ratios. Therefore, the inference of multilinear rank is more challenging when missing values occur.

As shown in (9), we employ a hierarchical group sparsity prior over the factor matrices and core tensor with aim to seek the minimum multilinear rank automatically, which is more efficient and elegant than the standard model selections by repeating many times and selecting one optimum model. By combining likelihood model in (8), we propose a Bayesian Tucker Completion (BTC) method, which enables us to infer the minimum multilinear rank as well as the noise level solely from partially observed data without requiring the tuning parameters.

To learn the BTC model, we employ the VB inference framework under a fully Bayesian treatment. In this section, we present only the main solutions. As can be derived, the variational posterior distribution over the core tensor \mathcal{G} is given by

$$q(\mathcal{G}) = \mathcal{N}\left(\text{vec}(\mathcal{G}) \mid \text{vec}(\tilde{\mathcal{G}}), \Sigma_G\right), \quad (10)$$

where the posterior parameters can be updated by

$$\text{vec}(\tilde{\mathcal{G}}) = \mathbb{E}[\tau]_{\Sigma_G} \sum_{(i_1, i_2, i_3) \in \Omega} \left(\mathcal{Y}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \bigotimes_{n=1}^3 \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)}] \right). \quad (11)$$

$$\Sigma_G = \left\{ \mathbb{E}[\beta] \bigotimes_n \mathbb{E}[\Lambda^{(n)}] + \mathbb{E}[\tau] \sum_{(i_1, i_2, i_3) \in \Omega} \bigotimes_{n=1}^3 \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)} \mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)T}] \right\}^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

Since the variational posterior distribution over $\{\mathbf{U}^{(n)}\}$ can be factorized as

$$q(\mathbf{U}^{(n)}) = \prod_{i_n} \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)} \mid \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{i_n}^{(n)}, \Psi_{i_n}^{(n)}\right), \quad n = 1, \dots, 3. \quad (13)$$

the posterior parameters are updated by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{i_n}^{(n)} = \mathbb{E}[\tau]_{\Psi_{i_n}^{(n)}} \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{G}_{(n)}] \sum_{(i_1, i_2, i_3) \in \Omega} \left(\mathcal{Y}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \bigotimes_{k \neq n} \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{u}_{i_k}^{(k)}] \right). \quad (14)$$

$$\Psi_{i_n}^{(n)} = \left\{ \mathbb{E}[\Lambda^{(n)}] + \mathbb{E}[\tau] \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{G}_{(n)} \Phi_{i_n}^{(n)} \mathbf{G}_{(n)}^T] \right\}^{-1}. \quad (15)$$

$$\Phi_{i_n}^{(n)} = \sum_{(i_1, \dots, i_N) \in \Omega} \bigotimes_{k \neq n} \mathbf{u}_{i_k}^{(k)} \mathbf{u}_{i_k}^{(k)T}. \quad (16)$$

The summation is performed over the observed data locations whose mode- n index is fixed to i_n . In other words, $\Phi_{i_n}^{(n)}$ represents the statistical information of mode- k ($k \neq n$) latent

factors that interact with $\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)}$. In (15), the complex posterior expectation can be computed efficiently by

$$\text{vec} \left\{ \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbf{G}_{(n)} \Phi_{i_n}^{(n)} \mathbf{G}_{(n)}^T \right] \right\} = \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbf{G}_{(n)} \otimes \mathbf{G}_{(n)} \right] \text{vec} \left(\Phi_{i_n}^{(n)} \right). \quad (17)$$

The variation posterior distribution over $\{\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(n)}\}$ is i.i.d. Gamma distributions due to the conjugate priors, which is $\forall n = 1, \dots, 3$,

$$q(\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(n)}) = \prod_{r_n=1}^{R_n} \text{Ga} \left(\lambda_{r_n}^{(n)} \mid \tilde{a}_{r_n}^{(n)}, \tilde{b}_{r_n}^{(n)} \right). \quad (18)$$

where the posterior parameters can be updated by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{a}_{r_n}^{(n)} &= a_0^\lambda + \frac{1}{2} \left(I_n + \prod_{k \neq n} R_k \right), \\ \tilde{b}_{r_n}^{(n)} &= b_0^\lambda + \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbf{u}_{r_n}^{(n)T} \mathbf{u}_{r_n}^{(n)} \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}[\beta] \mathbb{E} \left[\text{vec}(\mathcal{G}^2_{\dots r_n \dots})^T \right] \otimes_{k \neq n} \mathbb{E}[\boldsymbol{\lambda}^{(k)}]. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Finally, the predictive distributions over missing entries, given observed entries, can be approximated by using variational posterior distributions $q(\Theta)$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathcal{Y}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \mid \mathcal{Y}_\Omega) &= \int p(\mathcal{Y}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \mid \Theta) p(\Theta \mid \mathcal{Y}_\Omega) d\Theta \\ &\approx \mathcal{N} \left(\mathcal{Y}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \mid \tilde{\mathcal{Y}}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}, \mathbb{E}[\tau]^{-1} + \sigma_{i_1 i_2 i_3}^2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where the posterior parameters can be obtained by

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{Y}}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} &= \left(\otimes_n \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)T} \right] \right) \mathbb{E}[\text{vec}(\mathcal{G})], \\ \sigma_{i_1 i_2 i_3}^2 &= \text{Tr} \left(\mathbb{E} \left[\text{vec}(\mathcal{G}) \text{vec}(\mathcal{G})^T \right] \otimes_n \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)} \mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)T} \right] \right) \\ &\quad - \mathbb{E}[\text{vec}(\mathcal{G})]^T \left(\otimes_n \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)} \right] \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbf{u}_{i_n}^{(n)T} \right] \right) \mathbb{E}[\text{vec}(\mathcal{G})]. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Therefore, our model can provide not only predictions over missing entries, but also the uncertainty of predictions, which is quite important for some specific applications.

4. Experiments Results

We verified the proposed method experimentally and compared it with related methods, i.e., high accuracy low rank

tensor completion (HaLRTC) [8]. Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) [36] algorithm, developed in the 1970s, was employed by HaLRTC to solve the nuclear norm optimization problems with multiple non-smooth terms. HaLRTC algorithm using ADMM framework is based on simple low rank tensor completion (SiLRTC) algorithm [8]. By replacing the dummy matrices M_{i_s} by their tensor versions, the algorithm is shown in Algorithm (1).

Algorithm 1 HaLRTC Algorithm

- 1: Input: \mathcal{X} with $\mathcal{X}_\Omega = \mathcal{T}_{\Omega, p}$ and K
 - 2: Output: \mathcal{X}
 - 3: Set $\mathcal{X}_\Omega = \mathcal{T}_\Omega$ and $\mathcal{X}_{\bar{\Omega}} = 0$
 - 4: **for** $k = 0$ to K **do**
 - 5: **for** $i = 1$ to n **do**
 - 6: $\mathcal{M}_i = \text{fold}_i \left[D_{\frac{\alpha_i}{\rho}} \left(\mathcal{X}_{(i)} + \frac{1}{\rho} \mathcal{Y}_{i(i)} \right) \right]$
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: $\mathcal{X}_\Omega = \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{M}_i - \frac{1}{\rho} \mathcal{Y}_i \right)_{\bar{\Omega}}$
 - 9: $\mathcal{Y}_i = \mathcal{Y}_i - \rho(\mathcal{M}_i - \mathcal{X})$
 - 8: **end for**
-

4.1 MRI Completion

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a medical imaging and widely used in the clinical diagnosis [37]. We evaluate our method by using MRI data (<http://brainweb.bic.mni.mcgill.ca/brainweb>), this dataset contains a set of realistic MRI data volumes produced by an MRI simulator. Because MRI data is high-dimensional, the completion from sparse observations becomes very challenging. So we separate the high-dimensional tensor data into low-dimensional small tensors. Hence, our method can be applied to small tensors completion. In experiment, we use the size of small tensors in $50 \times 50 \times 50$.

We use missing ratio (20% - 50%) and consider the noises in MRI data, and evaluation the algorithms using Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PRSN) and RRSE. The result are shown in Table 1, and the visual quality is shown in Fig. 4. As we can see that the proposed method can effectively recover the missing values with high performance.

4.2 Video Completion

The video data is natural representation by a tensor as shown in Fig. 5. We evaluate the performance of the proposed method on a video sequence corrupted by additive Gaussian noise. The video sequence is downloaded from the benchmark data in [38]. We consider the noise standard deviation

Table 1: The Performance of MRI Completion Evaluated by PSNR and RRSE

Methods	Missing 50%		Missing 40%		Missing 30%		Missing 20%	
	Original	Noisy	Original	Noisy	Original	Noisy	Original	Noisy
BTC-T	PSNR RRSE 27.27 0.11	PSNR RRSE 26.42 0.12	PSNR RRSE 27.84 0.10	PSNR RRSE 27.12 0.11	PSNR RRSE 28.12 0.10	PSNR RRSE 27.55 0.11	PSNR RRSE 28.38 0.10	PSNR RRSE 27.83 0.10
HaLRTC	PSNR RRSE 24.19 0.16	PSNR RRSE 23.17 0.18	PSNR RRSE 26.73 0.12	PSNR RRSE 25.00 0.14	PSNR RRSE 29.57 0.085	PSNR RRSE 26.69 0.12	PSNR RRSE 32.93 0.057	PSNR RRSE 28.22 0.099

of 0.03, 0.15, 0.27 and missing ratio of 20% - 50%. The results are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 5: Tensor representation of a video sequence

Table 2: The Performance of Video Completion Evaluated by RRSE

	Missing				
	60%	50%	40%	30%	20%
Noise	RRSE	RRSE	RRSE	RRSE	RRSE
0.03	0.645	0.559	0.476	0.397	0.325
0.15	0.646	0.561	0.480	0.402	0.336
0.27	0.650	0.564	0.483	0.408	0.344

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed a image completion method based on Bayesian Tucker decomposition. By using variational bayesian inference, we can avoids the computational demanding rank selection procedure. We apply the proposed method to image and video with 20-50 % missing voxels, the experimental results demonstrate that our method can effectively recover the whole data with a high predictive performance.

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Fig. 4: Visualization of MRI data completion obtained by BTC

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